

Supersymmetry:A symmetry between space and mass

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Abstract: Space is divergent,while mass is convergent, and the two are symmetrical to each other. Here divergence and convergence are properties of functions in mathematics. What I mean is, space is diverging in the manner of functions! At the microscopic scale, we cannot directly observe the divergence of space, but we can describe it through the behavior of quantum. The divergence of space is perfectly aligns with the four types of divergence in functions: (1)Functions tend to infinity(The macrocosmic space tends to infinity); (2)Jump Discontinuity (Quantum discreteness); (3)Functions oscillate repeatedly between multiple values (Quantum superposition); (4)Unbounded Oscillation (Quantum particles oscillate in extra spatial dimensions; String Theory). Since the divergence of space and the convergence of mass are symmetric to each other, at the microscopic scale, the stronger the divergence of space, the stronger the convergence of mass(Asymptotic Freedom; Quark Confinement); at the macroscopic scale, the stronger the convergence of mass, the stronger the divergence of space(so treating gravity with quantum mechanics inevitably diverges to infinity).

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First,I will introduce two mathematical properties[1]:

(一) Divergence of functions:

1. Tend to infinity: The function tends to infinity;
2. Jump Discontinuity: Unequal One-sided Limits, Discontinuous divergence;
3. Bounded Oscillation: The function oscillates repeatedly between two or more values

(Uncertainty);

4. Unbounded Oscillation: The function oscillates repeatedly between positive and negative values with increasing amplitude, and finally the oscillation amplitude tends to infinity. When the oscillation amplitude tends to infinity, system symmetry breaking.

(二) Convergence of functions:

- 1.The function infinitely approaches a certain state or value(Certainty).

Substitute these two functional properties into space and mass respectively:

(一) Divergence of Space:

1. Space tends to infinity(The macrocosmic space tends to infinity);
2. Space diverges in a discontinuous manner (Quantum Discreteness);
3. Space oscillates repeatedly between two or more forms(Quantum superposition[2]);
4. Space oscillates repeatedly between the normal spatial-dimensions and the extra spatial-dimensions with increasing amplitude, and finally the oscillation amplitude tends to

infinity(as the oscillation amplitude of the space function increases, the universe's morphology transitions between the five superstring theories, and when the oscillation amplitude tends to infinity, the symmetry of the universe breaks gradually).

(二) Convergence of mass:

1. Mass infinitely approaches a certain form or value.

The smaller the spatial scale, the stronger the divergence of space: when the spatial distance tends to zero, the divergence of space tends to infinity. The greater the mass, the stronger the convergence of matter: when the mass tends to infinity, the convergence of matter tends to infinity.

Since space diverges in the manner of functions, it possesses four characteristics: Tend to infinity, Discreteness, Bounded Oscillation, Unbounded Oscillation.

Wave function collapse: for particles, space is diverging(wave nature), while mass/relativistic mass is converging(particle nature). Since the divergence of space and the convergence of mass are symmetric to each other, the stronger the divergence of space, the stronger the convergence of mass, the addition of any mass or energy will cause particles to transition from the divergent state to the convergent state(from wave nature to particle nature).

The space function oscillates repeatedly among multiple values, when mass and the energy it carries infinitely approaches one of these values, symmetry is formed between the two, endowing the particle with a stable structure. This is the fundamental principle of particle formation. When mass and the energy it carries increase, reaching a symmetry with space functions on a larger spatial scale, homologous particles with similar properties are formed.

Inside the atom, quanta formed by the same spatial function are in an entangled state; when the spatial function oscillates, quantum manifests as quantum spin. The symmetry between divergence and convergence is not a strict equivalence relation, the same spatial function oscillates repeatedly between two or more values, so an energy difference exists within the same energy level(Lamb shift[3]).

When the spatial scale approaches zero, mass inevitably converges to form composite particles in order to maintain the symmetry of divergence and convergence(the mass gap in the Yang-Mills equations[4]).

Since the divergence of space and the convergence of mass are symmetric to each other:

At the microscopic scale,the stronger the divergence of space,the stronger the convergence of mass (Asymptotic Freedom[5-6]; Quark confinement).

At the macroscopic scale,the stronger the convergence of mass,the stronger the divergence of space (The space within a black hole inevitably diverges to infinity).

Dark energy is the extreme manifestation of the divergence of space in the absence of mass.

Black holes are the extreme manifestation of the convergence of mass in the absence of space.

The symmetry of universe is undergoing accelerated polarization, with matter becoming

increasingly concentrated and the universe expanding at an accelerated rate.

This corresponds to unbounded oscillation in the divergence of the space: as the oscillation amplitude gradually increases, the symmetry of the universe breaks progressively.

Inside a galaxy, rotation leads to an increase in the divergence of space, causing matter to produce convergence(dark matter) based on symmetry. The convergence(dark matter) permeates the galactic interior, thereby maintaining the galaxy's stable structure.

Similarly, the convergence of mass permeates the interior of the particle, endowing it with a stable structure, when the particle is broken, the energy converges to form the particle. We refer to this class of particles as bosons.

Therefore, dark matter is composed of bosons, they are solely responsible for mediating gravity.

In summary:

(1) Space diverges in the manner of functions. Cosmic space is a vast divergent field.

(2) The divergence of space and the convergence of mass are symmetrical to each other.

Space diverges at infinity, mass converges at a point, when the divergence of space and the convergence of mass remain symmetrical, the matter possess a stable structure.

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